

LEARNER EFFECTIVENESS: A CAUSE OF LEARNER STRATEGY USE?

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Annotation:

The article indicates that researchers have developed strategies to determine which one will be more effective for students in teaching a second language (Ellis 2008). Agreeing to this reason, the researchers processed three steps for the students, which the first was training strategy questionnaire, which consists of two parts, 40 items, in accordance with the strategy questionnaire by Wong and Nunan (2011). Secondly, for this study, they selected students in the first year of postgraduate studies from Eastern Azerbaijan province as participants, 441 students of which were 224 boys and 217 girls. Third, they sent a survey questionnaire to selected participants and asked them to complete it. Ultimately, the researchers used the chi-square test to validate the collected research data. The study found significant differences between more effective and less effective use of language strategies by English learners. As a result of these studies, it was clarified that curriculum designers should include specific parts in the teaching materials for EFL classes, in which students are introduced to various learning strategies and learn to use the most effective strategies for completing language learning tasks. It has also been said that target language teachers should introduce their students to various strategies for dominating a second language.

Key words: Learning strategy, curriculum, second language acquisition, communicative competence, chi-square test, survey.

Students who were proposed as participants in the analysis were those who passed the same entrance exams, that is, subjects that were developed from different sections of the school curriculum. These students were between 18 and 22 years old. Also, the researchers, in order to select students, decided to accept based on the level of knowledge of the English language. To do this, they divided the choice into two groups, that is, students who are more knowledgeable and less fluent in English. Based on this, they had to divide the students again into two groups: there were points out of 100, more effective students who received 66 and less effective students who received 33 points.

The research process clarified the differences between students with high and low indicators in the study of strategies. It became known from the results of data analysis that there were clear differences between the groups of participants who were identified by six points and they include 6,9,12,13,27,33 items. The results of them showed that on these points students love to learn the language using different methods. For example: 6 - through reading, 9 - through conversation, 12 - through their own textbooks, 13 - through explanation everything by teacher, 27 - through English words by hearing them and 3 - by talking to friends in English.

The researchers considered it necessary to further study the problem in various fields of study and repeat this in many other educational institutions. It is also proposed in further research to find out the characteristics of the student, age group, learning styles on the relationship between the effectiveness of the student and the use of the strategy. Finally, it is recommended that future research investigate the different student differences in the context of second language learning. It is imperative to determine the level of knowledge of the student

in teaching English. It is also important to research and find out which strategies are most suitable for different students and teach them using this method in order to make it easier and better for students to learn a target language. This article helped me to understand the difference between learners and methods which can be used for their education. Also that even students should know different strategies, they can find which they prefer more and which will be more effective for their education. Of course, in this, teachers need help to find a suitable method for their students, guide them and work with their students to achieve the goal of teaching a target language at the highest level.

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